

COMPARISON OF RESPONSE OF GROOVED COMPOSITES TO LOADING VIA SPHERICAL AND CYLINDRICAL INDENTERS

H.K. Jeffrey^{1*}, P.A. Lagace¹, J.S. Iqbal²

¹ Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, ² The Boeing Company, Seattle, Washington, USA

* Corresponding author (holly_j@mit.edu)

The effects of two loading configurations on grooved composite specimens were assessed experimentally and using finite element analysis. A cylinder is used to apply a load along the length of the groove for a “two-dimensional (2-D) loading” case, and a sphere tip is used for a “three-dimensional (3-D) loading”. Laminates are subjected to these two loadings in order to better understand the effects of added complexity on the response of the composite. In all cases, the load was applied in the groove, perpendicular to the fibers of the specimen. Two types of tests were utilized: testing to final failure, and testing to initial permanent deformation, in the form of crushing. A thick composite specimen of 78 to 80 plies, with a length of 2 inches and width of 1 inch was created with a groove in the top surface. A total of 90 specimens were tested. A computed microtomography technique was used to examine selected specimens after testing, primarily to look for crushing damage. Finite element modeling was completed via ABAQUS for the same laminate configurations as in the experimental work, and both loading cases. A 2-D model was used for the cylinder loading, and the ball-ended indenter case was modeled via a 3-D model. Results of testing show the responses of the “2-D loading” and “3-D loading” are generally dissimilar, from initial damage to final failure. The “2-D loading” cases show several different behavior types for the load-stroke response, whereas only one behavior type occurs for the “3-D loading”. In the “3-D loading” specimens, there is evidence that crushing plays a significant role in the response of the specimen to loading. This is also indicated from the modeling results where higher contact pressure and through-thickness stresses occur for the “3-D loading”. Modeling work generally shows significant differences between the 2-D and 3-D cases. However, it is indicated that the 2-D models can be used for initial assessment, whereas 3-D modeling needs to be completed for final details. Furthermore, the “3-D loading” should be used for experiments, as crushing is not shown for “2-D loading”. Recommendations for further work are presented.

Keywords: *groove, transverse loading, laminate configuration, crushing, indentation*

1 Introduction

Current applications for the use of composite materials are generally limited to relatively simple geometries and applications where the loading occurs in the plane of the fibers. In order to further expand the use of composites in new applications with more complex geometries, the behavior of the materials when subject to an out-of-plane loading, as well as in-plane loading, needs to be better understood.

One potential use of composites in such a configuration is the telescopic wing spar, such as that developed by Czajkowski et al [1]. In this design, ball bearings connect sections of grooved composite spars. Load is transferred from one section to the next via these bearings. This would generate concentrated contact loads in the grooves in the composite laminate.

Out-of-plane loadings have been examined in the literature. However, this work has primarily considered impact loadings. A review of such work

has been completed by Abrate [2,3]. As a substitution and similarity for complex dynamic testing, quasi-static testing has also received considerable attention in the literature [e.g. 4-8], and this work lead to the development of ASTM Standard D6264 to measure the damage resistance of laminated composites plates via concentrated quasi-static indentation [9].

Relatively little work has considered grooved composites. Those that have done so generally consider a specific application rather than general issues. For example, Montay et al. examined residual stresses that result from flat grooves being incrementally drilled into a composite laminate [10]. Hoppel et al. developed a buttress groove to transmit shear load [11]. Romanoski and Burchell focused on improving the shear strength of the threads in a filament-wound composite cylinder [12]. However, none of these works considered the general characterization of the response of a grooved laminate structure subjected to out-of-plane loading.

An analytical investigation of a grooved composite specimen subjected to out-of-plane load via a cylindrical indenter was conducted by Bastien and Lagace [13]. In this work, two- and three-dimensional finite element models were used to examine isotropic and laminated specimens, with uniform loading along the groove for the three-dimensional model.

Kobayashi et al. developed a test method via a cylindrical indenter to examine the response of grooved composites when subjected to transverse loading [14,15]. This work aimed to isolate the response of the CRFP specimen around the groove, and the groove loading, from other effects. A specimen with a length of 2 inches, a width of 1 inch, and a maximum groove depth of 1/8 inch was developed. To accompany this, a test method was developed using a rigid backface boundary condition.

With the exception of the work by Bastien and Kobayashi, very little has been done to observe the response of a grooved composite subject to loads perpendicular to the in-plane fibers of the laminate, or loads in the groove [13-15]. The experimental procedures developed by Kobayashi are employed in the current work, and the loading configuration with the cylindrical indenter is considered to be the “two-dimensional loading” case without variation in the loading along the groove in this work. The uniform loading of the specimen along the groove is used on multiple laminates, and modified to study a nonuniform loading in the groove. The experimental configuration is extended to a spherical indenter. This is considered to be the “three-dimensional loading” case with variation in the loading along the groove. The assumptions in the modeling work by Bastien are examined in this work, and the modeling is expanded to cover the nonuniform loading along the groove.

2 Objectives and Approach

The primary objective of this work is to better understand the response of grooved composite configurations, with the goal of establishing the knowledge base to lead toward the understanding of the behavior of configurations such as a grooved composite telescopic spar. Specifically, the objective is to understand the effect of a “two-dimensional (2-D) loading” and a “three-dimensional (3-D) loading” on the response of grooved composite specimens. These two loadings are accomplished via a cylindrical indenter and a spherical indenter, respectively. The effects of these

two loading configuration on grooved composite specimens are assessed experimentally and using finite element models.

These configurations are subjected to these two loadings in order to better understand the effects of added complexity on the response of the composite. For the “2-D loading” case, a cylinder is used to apply a load along the length of the groove for the experimental specimen developed by Kobayashi et al. [14,15]. A schematic of this case is shown in Figure 1a. This generates a 2-D applied loading and resulting response, as the stress-strain state of the specimen is constant along the length of the groove, with no variation along the width (y-direction in Figure 1a) of the specimen. The “3-D loading” case is used to investigate the response of the specimen when subjected to a load that would be generated by a ball bearing. This is considered to be a “3-D loading” case as there is variation in the load distribution and resulting response along the width (y-direction in Figure 1b) of the specimen, as well as the other dimensions of the specimen. A schematic of this case is shown in Figure 1b. The originally developed test method was modified to achieve this loading.

These two cases are examined experimentally and via finite element models. In order to understand the response of the grooved composite specimen, and to observe the effects of ply angle and laminate configuration, a variety of laminate configurations are subjected to the two loading cases: $[\pm 45/0/90]_{10S}$, $[90/0]_{20S}$, and $[\pm 0/0]_{13S}$ with θ equal to 15° , 30° , 45° , and 60° . The material used throughout is a Toray Composites P707AG-15 unidirectional prepregged material with Toray T700GC-12K-31E carbon fibers and Toray Composites #2510 epoxy matrix. The material has a fiber volume fraction of approximately 65% and a nominal ply thickness of 0.006 ± 0.0004 in. The unidirectional ply properties for this material are shown in Table 1.

3 Experimental Work

A thick composite specimen of 78 to 80 plies, with a length of 2 inches and width of 1 inch was created. Composite plates were cured via autoclave using the temperature, pressure, and vacuum cycles recommended by the material manufacturer, but with a slower temperature ramp up, in order to allow for an even cure of the thick laminate. The cured plate was cut into the blocks, with 2-inch by 1-inch in-plane dimensions, using a 220-grit diamond-coated circular saw mounted on a milling machine. The groove is 1/4 inch in diameter, and machined

along the top surface of the width using a 2200-grit diamond coated end mill. A laser measurement and xy-positioning system was used to document the groove depth and verify good manufacturing.

In all cases, the load is applied in the groove, perpendicular to the fibers of the specimen. The “2-D loading case” is created via a 1-inch cylinder with a radius of 0.25 inches, made of M2/M7 steel with a Rockwell hardness of C62 to C64, as Kobayashi found softer steel cylinders deformed before final failure of the composite specimen [14,15]. A ball-ended indenter was developed for the “3-D loading” case as a ball bearing did not allow for sufficient displacement of the load applicator. Initial testing showed that the load applicator for this case would need to allow for significant displacement and prevent extra contact between the specimen and indenter during testing. The ball-ended indenter is made of maraging steel. It has a hemispherical end with a 0.25-inch diameter, and a 0.5-inch long cylinder with the same diameter. However, it is filleted to a base with a 0.5-inch diameter, and the overall length is 0.75 inches. The maraging steel is initially soft for machining, but after heat treatment has a Rockwell hardness of C48. Full details of the experimental study can be found in the work by Jeffrey [16].

Overall there are four test types used in this work, with two test cases for each of the two loading configurations. The two test cases involve the type of damage: testing to final failure, and testing to initial permanent deformation, in the form of crushing. All tests were performed using a hydraulic MTS machine with a 200 kN load cell. Rigid backface boundary conditions were used in order to eliminate bending effects but allow unrestricted deformation in the x- and y-directions. The -z face of the specimen rested on a steel plate on the order of 1/4 inch in thickness in order to produce the rigid backface boundary condition. The specimen is free to deform in the length and width directions. A stroke control rate of 0.004 in/min is used for all tests. Load and stroke data were recorded at a rate of 1 Hz. For failure tests, testing continues until either a sudden load drop of at least 50% of the maximum load occurs, or a persistent inability to carry additional load occurs. The persistent inability to carry additional load is defined as a stroke of 0.25 mm with no increase in load beyond the maximum load. The latter typically occurs in the “3-D loading” case.

A total of 81 specimens were manufactured and tested in this work, with an additional 9 specimens

from previous work also considered. Of these, 46 specimens were tested using the “2-D loading” configuration, with 28 tested to final failure and 18 tested for crushing. In tests to final failure, 9 quasi-isotropic specimens were tested in the previous work [14,15], 5 cross-ply specimens were tested, and 3 or 5 of each of the $[\pm\theta/0]_{13S}$ specimens were tested. For the crushing tests, three of each laminate were tested. For the “3-D loading” configurations, 44 specimens were tested, with 26 tested to final failure and 18 tested for crushing. For these failure tests, 5 specimens of the quasi-isotropic, cross-ply, $[\pm45/0]_{13S}$ and $[\pm30/0]_{13S}$ laminates were tested, and 3 of the $[\pm15/0]_{13S}$ and $[\pm60/0]_{13S}$. For the crushing tests, three of each laminate were tested.

In the tests for crushing, the specimens are initially loaded to an indenter/machine-head displacement of 0.012 inches. This value was chosen based on initial tests which show no permanent deformation occurred at this level. The specimen is then unloaded, and the laser measurement and xy-positioning system is used to check for permanent deformation, as compared to the initial measurements. This process is repeated, incrementally increasing the load and displacement, until crushing is detected, as subsequently defined. For the “3-D loading” configuration, a 1 kN increment was used, and crushing is considered to have occurred once the groove depth changes by more than one standard deviation of the initially measured groove depth, at any point where there was indenter contact. The loading increment was determined from initial testing and minimizes loading-unloading cycles and therefore potential loading location errors. For the “2-D loading” configuration, a 5 kN increment was used to limit the number of loading-unloading cycles. These values also were determined from initial testing, and crushing was considered to have occurred once the average groove depth was at least one standard greater than the originally measured depth.

After testing, several specimens were examined using computed microtomography (μ CT), a non-destructive X-ray technique that allows for the examination of the entire volume of a specimen. In this process, many X-ray readings of a sample are taken, and these readings are then used to virtually reconstruct the specimen via computer. A series of “virtual cuts” can then be made using the computer and the data taken. These are used to examine the interior damage of the specimens. One specimen for each laminate configuration after testing to crushing was examined for each of the two loading cases.

These were randomly selected as there were no externally visible distinguishing characteristics. Crushing was of particular interest as this is the first sign of permanent damage.

4 Finite Element Modeling

In order to examine the stress state of the grooved composite configurations, finite element modeling was completed via ABAQUS. This was done for the same laminate configurations as in the experimental work, and for both the “2-D” and “3-D loading” cases. As in the experimental testing, rigid backface boundary conditions were employed in the models to eliminate global effects of bending, but allow unrestricted deformation in the x- and y-directions.

A 2-D study was completed to examine the accuracy of the Hertzian contact pressure method previously employed to apply loads to the grooved composites [13]. These results showed that the Hertzian method was not a good approximation of the contact pressure that arose from applying a load to the groove via an indenter. Thus, a rigid body indenter was created in this modeling work, and the load applied via this body to the groove. The validity of the assumption of a rigid body was also investigated with a 2-D model. In the z-direction, a steel indenter is much stiffer than the composite, by approximately a factor of 25. This is not the case in the plane of the fibers. A linear-elastic indenter was thus considered for the 2-D model. The results showed that the rigid body approximation of the steel indenter is sufficiently accurate to capture the laminate behavior due to the large difference in stiffness between the high-stiffness steel and the low stiffness of the composite in the through-thickness direction. This rigid body approximation also saved cost of computation. Full details of these initial models and the full finite element work can be found in the work by Iqbal [17].

A 2-D model is used for the cylinder loading, i.e. “2-D loading”, case with continuum, plane strain, 4-node, linear, quadrilateral, isoparametric, reduced integration (CPE4R) elements. The “3-D loading” case, with the ball-ended indenter, requires a 3-D model with continuum, 3-D, 8-node, linear, hexahedral, isoparametric, reduced integration (C3D8R) elements. The meshes for all models were generated with automatic meshing routines available in ABAQUS, although the node density is higher in regions closer to the groove. There are larger stress gradients in the region close to the groove, and the meshing accounts for this. Each of the six laminate configurations considered in the experimental work

was modeled with the 2-D and 3-D models. For both models, a rigid body indenter was modeled, either via a circle representing a cylinder, or a sphere representing a ball bearing and the ball-ended indenter. Loads were applied to these rigid bodies, and the linear-elastic composite specimen deformed around these bodies as rigid displacement of the body was enforced. The 3-D model, which employs a rigid sphere to apply a load, is a more realistic representation of the grooved composite structure in contact with ball bearings. However, this model is only a small section of the grooved composite with a single ball bearing, with much of the complexity removed as it effectively isolates a single ball bearing.

Three mesh regions were defined for the 2-D model of the “2-D loading” case, with the mesh nodes closer together in the region of the groove. An illustration of the mesh regions is shown in Figure 2. In Region 1, the nodes are 0.001 inches apart along the groove and 0.002 inches elsewhere in the x-direction. The node distance is 0.003 inches in the z-direction. In Region 2, the x-direction nodes are 0.002 inches apart at the top of the region (the intersection with the bottom of Region 1), and 0.003 inches apart at the lower surface of the model. As in Region 1, the mesh nodes are 0.003 inches apart in the z-direction to give two elements per ply. For Region 3, as in the other regions, the z-direction node distance is 0.003 inches. There are 16 nodes per edge in the x-direction in this region, with a bias ratio of 4.0.

Cost of computation for the 3-D model, which is necessary for the “3-D loading” case as there is variation in the load along the y-direction, is much higher than that for the 2-D model. In order to alleviate this cost, a plane of symmetry in the yz-plane along the groove is imposed, as shown in Figure 3. This is not ideal as it produces stress concentrations in the angled plies near the plane of symmetry. The mesh is specifically designed to minimize the number of elements, while still concentrating elements near the groove and contact region, where there are large stress concentrations and stress gradients. A top-down view of the mesh on the top surface of the specimen, which changes in the z-direction in the groove, can be seen in Figure 4. As in the case of the 2-D model, the 3-D model is divided into three regions for meshing. These regions include the entire thickness of the specimen at a given (x, y) location. Region 1 encompasses the entire region of the groove where contact occurs, and the mesh is finest in this region. From the center

of the specimen, Region 1 extends two groove radii, 0.25 inches, in the x-direction from the center of the groove, and one groove radii, 0.125 inches, in either direction along the y-direction of the specimen. Region 2 includes the remainder of the groove region and extends in the x-direction for the same distance as Region 1. Regions 1 and 2 share a common mesh cross-section in the xz-plane, perpendicular to the groove, which is swept along the y-direction to form a 3-D mesh. From the top surface through 9 plies and the depth of the groove, there are 20 elements with a bias ratio of 3.0, where there are more elements near the groove. From the bottom of the groove to the specimen midplane, there are 50 elements with a bias ratio of 3.0, with larger elements farther from the groove. For the remainder of the specimen thickness, there are 28 elements with a bias ratio of 2.0. In areas of interest, i.e. near the contact in the groove, there are at least 2 elements per ply, through the thickness. Elsewhere there is 1 element per ply, through the thickness. This xz-plane mesh is swept through Regions 1 and 2, with 24 elements and a bias ratio of 17.0 in Region 1 and 7 elements and a bias ratio of 6.0 in Region 2. Region 3, which does not encompass the contact area or any features of interest, has the coarsest mesh and includes the majority of the volume of the specimen. This mesh was defined in the xy-plane and swept through the thickness of the laminate. This region has 8 elements in the x-direction with a bias ratio of 8.0, with more elements near the groove.

Each of the laminate configurations tested in the “2-D loading” and “3-D loading” cases in the experimental work were modeled with the 2-D model and 3-D model for a rigid indenter.

5 Experimental Results

Loading configurations are compared based on load and stroke data recorded during the tests. Key observations and associated thoughts are subsequently presented.

For the “2-D loading” case, several elements of the load-stroke response were used to compare the specimens. These include the maximum load reached during testing, the slope of an initial linear region of behavior, and the slope of a second linear region. In addition, many of the specimens have a “knee load”, immediately after which the slope of the response was less than that in the initial linear region, and/or “reverse knee load”, where the slope of the response increases.

Four representative load versus stroke curves capture the behavior shown in all the cases. These “Behavior Types” are based on the characteristics of the initial slope, the second slope, the knee load, and the reverse knee load. A representative load-stroke curve illustrating all of these features for a particular Behavior Type is shown in Figure 5. These Behavior Types are:

Behavior Type A: There is an initial linear region of behavior preceding a knee load. This is followed by a region with a decrease in slope and then a reverse knee load. The second linear region, which follows the reverse knee load, has a slope that is approximately equal to the slope of the initial linear region.

Behavior Type B: There is an initial linear region of behavior preceding a knee load. This is followed by a region with a decrease in slope and then a reverse knee load (similar to Behavior Type A). The second linear region, which follows the reverse knee load, has a slope that is greater (at least 8.0 kN/mm, or 10%,) than that of the slope of the initial linear region.

Behavior Type C: There is an initial linear region preceding a knee load. The knee load leads to a second linear region. This linear region has a slope that is less (at least 7.9 kN/mm, or 8%) than that of the initial linear region. There is no reverse knee load.

Behavior Type D: There is an initial linear region preceding a reverse knee load. This initial linear region continues to a load significantly beyond the knee load of other Behavior Types. The reverse knee load is followed by a second linear region with a slope that is greater (at least 6.0 kN/mm, or 7%) than that of the slope of the initial linear region. There is no knee load.

Two of the laminates exhibit strictly one Behavior Type, as all specimens of the cross-ply $[90/0]_{20S}$ laminate show Behavior Type D, and all specimens of the $[\pm 15/0]_{13S}$ laminate show Behavior Type C. The quasi-isotropic $[\pm 45/0/90]_{10S}$ and $[\pm 60/0]_{13S}$ laminates, both exhibit Behavior Types A and B. These two types are very similar behaviors, as each has both the knee load and reverse knee load. The $[\pm 30/0]_{13S}$ laminate primarily exhibits Behavior Type C, without a reverse knee load following the knee load. However, one of these three specimens exhibits Behavior Type A, and with only three specimens for reference, this laminate could potentially exhibit both Behavior Types. The only laminate to exhibit more than two Behavior

Types is the $[\pm 45/0]_{13S}$ laminate, and this laminate shows all four Behavior Types in the load-stroke response. The Behavior Types and their association with specific laminates indicate that the specifics of the specimen and laminate for the distributed “2-D loading” case have a significant impact on the load-stroke response and failure.

Overall, the “2-D loading” specimens showed two failure modes. Both were governed by a sudden delamination. However, in some specimens, the delamination began approximately at the bottom of the groove. This is considered to be Mode A. In other specimens, a transverse crack initiated near the bottom of the groove, progressed through multiple plies, and lead to a delamination below the bottom of the groove. The transverse crack is at least 1/16 inch through the thickness. This is considered to be Mode B. These two failure modes are shown in Figure 6.

For those specimens that show either Behavior Type A or B, there is a direct correlation to either Failure Mode A or B. Behavior Type A corresponds to failure via Mode A, and Behavior Type B corresponds to failure via Mode B. Additionally, these Behavior Types and Failure Modes are related to the maximum load the specimen reaches. The maximum load for Behavior Type A is less than 110 kN, and for Behavior Type B is greater than 125 kN. This is indicative that there is likely a damage mode that occurs during the loading that affects the load-stroke response and failure.

Several specimens were examined and images reconstructed with the computed microtomography technique. However, while the damage in the “2-D loading” configuration was measured by laser as a change in the groove depth, there was no visible damage using the μ CT technique.

While the specimens loaded with the cylindrical indenter, i.e. “2-D loading”, exhibited several behavior types in the load-stroke response, the specimens loaded with the ball-ended indenter (i.e. “3-D loading”) displayed only one general behavior type. A representative load-stroke curve of such is shown in Figure 7. This behavior includes an initial region of linear slope, a knee load, and a second linear region, with a reduced slope, leading to the maximum load. This is the same general behavior as Behavior Type C in the “2-D loading” case.

There was one failure mode exhibited by the specimens loaded via the “3-D loading” configuration. The ball-ended indenter pushed into the laminate with this leading to a major delamination below the groove. This delamination

occurred 0.08 to 0.15 inches below the bottom of the groove. While this exhibits some of the external, post-mortem features as Failure Mode B in the “2-D loading” case, damage such as crushing and indenter penetration mask features that may identify this as a different failure mode.

In the specimens subjected to the “3-D loading” configuration and tested to the “crushing” load, the internal damage that occurs at permanent deformation can be seen. A series of “virtual cuts” of the reconstructed $[\pm 60/0]_{13S}$ specimen in this case show evidence of the internal damage at the “crushing” load. Clear evidence of a displaced ply can be seen in the reconstruction of the samples that are closer to unidirectional, i.e. the $[\pm 15/0]_{13S}$ and $[\pm 30/0]_{13S}$ cases, that were examined using μ CT. A displaced ply can be seen in the “virtual cut” shown in Figure 8. In contrast, the quasi-isotropic $[\pm 45/0/90]_{10S}$ laminate and cross-ply $[90/0]_{20S}$ laminate only showed damage via the indentation left from the ball-ended indenter at the bottom of the groove, as found using the laser measurement and xy-positioning system.

6 Modeling Results

The distribution of the contact pressure, the pressure that results on the surface of the groove from the load transmitted through the displaced rigid body, was examined. This pressure is normalized by the applied loading. For all laminates with the “2-D loading”, the maximum contact pressure occurs near the bottom of the groove. The ends of contact, where contact pressure reaches zero, occurs by ϕ , groove angle, equal to 50° , as shown in Figure 9. This groove angle is the angular component of the cylindrical coordinate system originating at the groove center of curvature. The bottom of the groove is where ϕ equals 0° . In the “3-D loading” case, maximum contact pressure again occurs at the bottom of the groove, and contact ends by ϕ close to 50° . However, a significant difference exists in the “3-D loading” case, as a large gradient of contact pressure in the y-direction with contact lost within 0.02 inches of the center of contact. This results in an elliptical footprint of contact with associated contact pressure gradients, as shown in Figures 10 and 11.

In all laminates, the pressure is basically independent of ply angle for groove angles close to the bottom of the groove. This behavior changes at groove angles ϕ , greater than 22.5° , as the pressure increases within 0° plies, and decreases within 90° and other angle plies. For all cases, the greater the

difference in ply angle between adjacent plies, the “ply angle mismatch”, the greater the change in contact pressure between the plies. This ply angle mismatch effect is related to the difference in ply stiffness between two plies of different angles. This effect becomes more pronounced as ϕ increases, due to an increase in the component of pressure applied along the longitudinal axis of the ply. In contrast, at lower values of ϕ , the pressure is more aligned with the through-thickness direction of the plies. Thus, this key stiffness is not dependent on ply angle, resulting in less ply-to-ply to no variation in contact pressure.

Plots of the isostress, normalized by applied loading, are used to further consider the response. Results show three primary regions as illustrated in Figure 12. Zone 1 extends from the bottom of the groove through to the back face of the laminate. In this region, the through-thickness normalized stress, σ_{zz}^* , shows a large compressive stress region beginning at the bottom of the groove, where there is indenter contact, and extending to the bottom of the specimen. The magnitude of the stress decreases farther from the point of contact with the region increasing in size. The integral of σ_{zz} over this area at any through-thickness location is equal to the applied contact loading. Furthermore, the distributions for this stress are very similar across all laminates, as the through-thickness stiffness does not vary with ply angle.

Normalized shear stress, σ_{xz}^* , in this region shows larger values near the point of highest σ_{zz}^* and dissipates quickly in all directions. This is linked through differential stress equilibrium to distribute the through-thickness extensional stress. Finally, the in-plane longitudinal stresses, σ_{xx}^* , are tensile or compressive in this region, depending on the ply angle. This is directly linked to a Poisson effect from the through-thickness stress and the in-plane ply stiffness in the direction of consideration. These longitudinal stresses are largest in the 0° plies, since these plies are stiffest in the in-plane x-direction. The large variation from ply to ply due to the greatly varying stiffness in the x-direction, as dependent on the ply angle, can be seen in Figures 13 and 14. In general, the greater the ply angle, the lower the stiffness of the ply in the x-direction as the fiber direction deviates farther from the x-direction. Thus, for all laminates, the difference in stress between neighboring plies is dependent on the difference in orientation angle between those plies, the “ply angle mismatch”, with a greater difference in angle resulting in a greater difference in stress.

Furthermore, in this region the integration through-thickness stress is close to zero as there is no to little net load applied in the in-plane directions.

The second general region of stresses, Zone 2, extends as the groove angle increases and ends at the point where contact is lost. This zone extends away from the groove through the body, approximately along these groove angles. In this region, the in-plane longitudinal stress, σ_{xx}^* , is primarily compressive as the contact pressure increases its in-plane component and directly causes this stress. Variations from ply to ply again occur due to relative ply stiffness in the direction of consideration. The shear stress, σ_{xz}^* , increases in this region largely due to the component of the contact pressure causing a shearing in the xz-plane. This occurs across the y-direction for the “2-D loading”, whereas there is a quick dropoff of this stress in the y-direction for the “3-D loading” due to the large gradient of the contact pressure in that direction.

The third general region of stresses, Zone 3, extends from the point of loss of contact pressure to the top of the laminate and outward into the body. There are virtually no through-thickness stresses, σ_{zz}^* , in this region. The in-plane longitudinal stresses, σ_{xx}^* , are tensile, smaller in magnitude than in the other zones, and quickly dissipate away from the groove. The Zone 3 stresses are due to the interaction of the structural deformation, the laminate stiffness, and ply-to-ply stiffnesses. The shear stresses, σ_{xz}^* , are also quite low in magnitude and related to other stress gradients.

It is noted that these general characteristics of the stresses and associated zones are similar for the “2-D loading” and “3-D loading” cases, except for the large gradient in the stresses along the y-direction for the 3-D case as is seen for the contact pressure. Such gradients end within 0.2 inches of the center of the specimen in the y-direction, decreasing in magnitude farther from the contact area.

Finally, the effect of load magnitude was investigated for both loading cases by considering a $[\pm 45/0/90]_{10S}$ laminate. In both cases, the area of contact changes size significantly and not in linear relation to the load magnitude. Thus, linear scaling of the response by the applied loading would be quite inaccurate. The specific results show that for the 2-D case, the contact ends at a groove angle of approximately 30° for the lower loading, as opposed to 50° for the higher loading. For the lower loading, the contact pressure, relative to the applied loading, is almost twice that for the higher loading. For the

3-D case, the elliptical contact footprint for the lower loading has an area that is approximately a factor of 2.75 smaller than for the higher loading case. The aspect ratio for this contact pressure ellipse also changes from approximately 7 to 9 when the load decreases. All normalized pressures in the distribution are significantly higher and with higher gradients for the lower loading. This is due to the need to distribute the load from the indenter over a smaller contact area.

7 Summary

Results show the responses of the cylindrical (“2-D loading”) and spherical (“3-D loading”) indenters are generally dissimilar, from initial damage to final failure. In the “3-D loading” specimens, there is evidence that crushing plays a significant role in the response of the specimen to loading. First, microtomography shows that localized crushing occurred in the “3-D loading” case, whereas crushing is not visible in the “2-D loading” case. Second, the finite element work shows that the response of the grooved laminate to either indenter does not vary linearly with the applied load, as the contact area between the indenter and groove changes with applied load. At the lower loads, with larger relative contact stresses, there are higher stresses and gradients in the specimen. In the 3-D model, there are high stress gradients in more directions than in the “2-D loading” case. This causes higher contact pressure at the bottom point of the sphere. This likely influences the early evidence of crushing that is seen in the experimental work. The use of nonlinear material behavior should be investigated in the modeling, particularly for the 3-D model where crushing was observed. High pressures and stresses local to contact are likely to lead to a nonlinear stress-strain response and may influence the crushing behavior.

In contrast to the “3-D loading” specimens that generally have similar load-stroke responses, the “2-D loading” cases show several different behaviors for the load-stroke response. This indicates that the specifics of the laminate configuration have a more direct effect on the “2-D loading” response, whereas the loading, and resultant crushing, has a more significant effect for the “3-D loading” case. The modeling work shows that the stress behavior, which directly influences the load-stroke response, is dependent on both the applied stress and laminate configuration, as was seen for the “2-D loading” specimens, with the differences in stresses between adjacent plies affected by the “ply angle mismatch”.

The change in pressure between neighboring plies is also dependent on the “ply angle mismatch”. This “ply angle mismatch” thus affects the load-stroke behavior exhibited in the experimental work for the “2-D loading” case, along with the ability of the laminate to resist indentation, as measured by the slope of the response.

There are significant differences in the results between the 2-D and 3-D models, particularly in determining the magnitude of the response. This includes the inability of the 2-D model to capture variation along the groove indicating the relationship of load to contact length. However, the 2-D model is sufficient to observe most trends in the stress field for the 3-D case, and therefore could be of use in preliminary design work, such as laminate selection. The 3-D model would then need to be used to determine the actual values of the contact pressures and the resulting stresses. The experimental “2-D loading” case would not provide useful data. The primary reason for this is that the “3-D loading” case allows the crushing to occur, which does not occur in the “2-D loading” case. Thus, experimental work would need to be conducted using the “3-D loading” configuration representing the simple case of one isolated ball bearing in the groove.

Further work investigating the effects of loading configuration should include conducting a nonlinear finite element investigation. Multiple loading points, as multiple ball bearings would create, and loading not perfectly perpendicular to the plies should also be considered in additional investigations to extend the base understanding established herein.

Property	Value
E_1 [Msi]	18.2
E_2 [Msi]	1.22
E_3 [Msi]	1.22
G_{12} [Msi]	0.613
G_{13} [Msi]	0.613
G_{23} [Msi]	0.399
ν_{12}	0.309
ν_{13}	0.309
ν_{23}	0.596

Table 1. Unidirectional ply properties for T700/2510 graphite/epoxy material.

Fig. 1. Schematic of (a) "2-D loading" case and (b) "3-D loading" case.

Fig. 2. Meshing regions for 2-D FEM for "2-D loading" case.

Fig. 3. Meshing regions for 3-D FEM for "3-D loading" case.

Fig. 4. 3-D FEM mesh of top surface, with elements highly concentrated near contact region.

Fig. 5. Load-stroke curve for Behavior Type A showing all features used to define Behavior Types.

Fig. 6. Photographs of (a) failure via Mode A, and (b) failure via Mode B.

Fig. 7. Representative load-stroke curve for "3-D loading" case.

Fig. 8. μ CT virtual cut showing displaced ply in a $[\pm 30/0]_{13S}$ specimen, 0.005 inches below the bottom of groove.

Fig. 9. Representative normalized contact pressure distribution for 2-D model.

Fig. 10. Representative elliptical contact pressure footprint for 3-D FEM.

Fig. 11. Representative normalized contact pressure distributions for several y-locations for 3-D FEM.

Fig. 12. Illustration of stress regions in models.

Fig. 13. Isostress plot of σ_{11}^* for cross-ply laminate from 2-D FEM.

Fig. 14. Isostress plot of σ_{xx}^* for cross-ply laminate from 3-D FEM.

References

- [1] M. Czajkowski, G. Clausen, and B. Sarh "Telescopic Wing of an Advanced Flying Automobile," AIAA Paper 1997-5602. presented at the World Aviation Congress, Anaheim, CA. October 1997.
- [2] S. Abrate "Impact on Laminated Composite Materials," *Applied Mechanics Review*, Vol. 44, No. 4, pp. 155–190, 1991.
- [3] S. Abrate "Impact on Laminated Composites: Recent Advances," *Applied Mechanics Review*, Vol. 47, No. 11, pp. 517–544, 1994.
- [4] P. Lagace, J. Williamson, P. Tsang, E. Wolf, and S. Thomas "A Preliminary Proposition for a Test Method to Measure (Impact) Damage Resistance," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics & Composites*, Vol. 12, No. 5, pp. 584–601, 1993.
- [5] W. Jackson and C. Poe, Jr. "The Use of Impact Force as a Scale Parameter for the Impact Response of Composite Laminates," *Journal of Composites Technology & Research*, Vol. 15, No. 4, pp. 282–289, 1993.
- [6] Y. Kwon and B. Sankar "Indentation-Flexure and Low-Velocity Impact Damage in Graphite Epoxy Laminates," *Journal of Composites Technology & Research*, Vol. 15, No. 2, pp. 101–111, 1993.
- [7] P. Sjöblom, J. Hartness, and T. Cordell "On Low-Velocity Impact Testing of Composite Materials,"

Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 22, No. 1, pp. 30–52, 1988.

- [8] S. Lee and P. Zahuta "Instrumented Impact and Static Indentation of Composites," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 25, No. 2, pp. 204–222, 1991.
- [9] ASTM D 6264/D 6264M - 12, Standard Test Method for Measuring the Damage Resistance of a Fiber-Reinforced Polymer-Matrix Composite to a Concentrated Quasi-Static Indentation Force. American Society for Testing and Materials, 2012.
- [10] G. Montay, O. Sicot, X. Gong, A. Cherouat, and J. Lu "Determination of the Residual Stresses in Composite Laminate using the Compliance Method," in *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Residual Stresses (ICRS-7)*, *Materials Science Forum*, 490–491, pp. 533–538, 2005.
- [11] C. Hoppel, T. Bogetti, and J. Gillespie, Jr. "Devices for Transmitting High Shear Loads in Composite Structures," in *Proceedings of the American Society for Composites 11th Technical Conference*, pp. 437–446, 1996.
- [12] G. Romanoski and T. Burchell "Method for Reinforcing Threads in Multilayer Composite Tubes and Cylindrical Structures," *Ceramic Engineering & Science Proceedings*, Vol. 17, No. 4, pp. 90–97, 1996.
- [13] C. Bastien and P. Lagace "Response of Grooved Laminated Plates to Out-of-Plane Contact Loading," in *Proceedings of the 50th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, 2009.
- [14] Y. Kobayashi, P. Lagace, and H. Jeffrey "A Test Specimen for Composite Laminates with Grooves Subjected to Out-of-Plane Contact Loading," in *Proceedings of the ASC 25th Technical Conference*, 2010.
- [15] Y. Kobayashi, "Establishment of an Experimental Method for a Grooved Composite Subjected to Out-of-Plane Contact Loading," S.M. Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2009.
- [16] H. Jeffrey, "Response of Grooved Composites to Transversely Distributed and Localized Spherical Contact Loadings," S.M. Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2011.
- [17] J. Iqbal "Response of Grooved Composites to Out-of-Plane Contact Loading via Numerical Models," S.M. Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2011.